

DEVELOPING BASIC COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS BASED ON INDIVIDUAL APPROACH

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Abstract. *The development of basic competencies of students based on an individual approach consists of several stages. The article describes the stages of confirmation of a competent approach, the views of scientists on the concept of an individual approach.*

Keywords: *purpose, communication, technology, approach, competence, information, society, science, didactics.*

Social values describe social communities of different scales (levels) and arise as a result of life activities of a particular society, reflect its main features. Social values are superior to individual consciousness and activity, and education is the main one in relation to individual psychological values [1].

Division into social and individual values is conditional. A.S. Makarenko's works show how the community and the individual can "enter" each other: the collective interest that appears to a person today, after some time, becomes personally significant and vice versa. Pedagogical skill also ends with the organization of the vital activity of the team and its relations; in which there is a continuous process of mutual enrichment of personal values with social values and vice versa. A.S. Makarenko is ahead of pedagogical practice and methodological theory in this matter and shows the inseparable unity of personal and social education [2].

What a person sees is limited by his individual point of view, therefore, leaving the child within his life experience and personal goals, virtualizing the generalized experience of humanity (including the teacher as the carrier of this generalized experience) - the development of his personality freely, spontaneously and in limited conditions ignores. Limiting the reader to only personal experience can lead him to choose immoral (even criminal) personal goals, which are very easily realized through communication technologies. Certain moral-intellectual parameters lead to the prediction of options for the goals of education, as a condition for the normal functioning of society and humanity in relation to each person in society.

The development of basic competencies of students based on an individual approach has always been the focus of researchers. Yu.A. Pervin stated that the competent approach to defining the goals and content of general education is not completely new and is not alien to the modern school [3]. The individual approach to education does not mean the individualization of a child by separating it from others, but it means the scientific understanding of the special conditions in the formation of certain characteristics of a person. The task of the individual approach is to determine the individual methods of development, to ensure the child's opportunities and the activity of each person [7].

"However, the chronological and content of the new approach indicates the philosophical expansion and development of modern didactics, the main science of the information society based on the fundamental conclusions of A.P. Ershov" [4]. In world educational practice, the concept of competence works as a central concept:

- competence includes intellectual and professional components of education;

- the concept of competence includes the ideology of interpreting the educational content formed from the "result";

- the core competence has an integrative nature, as it includes a number of similar skills and knowledge related to culture and broad areas of activity.

The definition of competence and competence in local pedagogy and psychology is given in the works of I.A.Zimnyaya [5], A.M.Novikov [6] and others. A competent approach is considered in the works of psychologist I.S. Yakimanskaya [7].

I.A.Zimnyaya distinguished three stages of developing a competent approach [5].

The first stage (1960s - 1970s) is characterized by the introduction of the category of "competence" into the scientific apparatus, the creation of necessary conditions for distinguishing the concepts of competence and competence.

The second stage (1970 - 1990) is mainly characterized by the use of categories of competence and competence in the theory and practice of teaching the mother tongue and in the field of administration and management. Foreign and domestic researchers in different types of activities begin to distinguish different competences and competences.

The third stage of approval of the competent approach (1990 - 2001) is characterized by the active use of competence and competence categories in education. UNESCO documents list a number of competencies that are considered desirable learning outcomes. In 1996, the Council of Europe introduces the concept of "basic competences", which should contribute to the maintenance of a democratic society, multilingualism, and meet the new requirements of the labor market and economic changes.

In the works of A.V. Khutorsky, it is said that "competence is a person's possession and acquisition of relevant competences, including his attitude towards him as a personal and activity subject". "Competence includes a set of interrelated qualities (knowledge, skills, skills, methods of activity) established by a person in relation to a certain range of objects and processes and necessary for high-quality production activities in relation to them" [8].

E.F. Zeer defines competencies as "meaningful generalizations of theoretical and empirical knowledge presented in the form of concepts, principles, meaningful rules" [9].

Competencies of the theoretical level of generalization reflect the internal connections and relations of objects and events of reality expressed in concepts, laws, principles, and their concretization.

Empirical competencies reflect the external characteristics of objects - events. They have a practical, effective character. The concretization of this level of generalization consists of words-terms, signs, symbols, procedural knowledge, pictures, examples.

Competence can be defined as a comprehensive and systematic set of knowledge summarized in its general form.

"Competencies are generalized ways of performing work that ensure effective performance of professional activity. It is the ability of a person to apply his competence in practice. The basis of competence is a set of activity skills - methods of action. The operational-technological component determines the essence of competence. Because the implementation of competencies occurs in the process of performing various activities to solve theoretical and practical issues, in addition to active (process) knowledge, skills and qualifications, the composition of competencies includes motivational and emotional-will areas. An important component of competencies is

experience - the integration of individual actions, methods and ways learned by a person in solving problems into a single whole" [9].

M.A. Kholodnaya defines competence as "a special type of organization of subject-related knowledge that allows effective decision-making in the relevant field of activity" and emphasizes the requirements that this type of knowledge must meet [10].

In the development of basic competencies of students based on an individual approach, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following:

- motivation, need and interest in acquiring technical, software and knowledge, skills and competences;

- a set of social, natural and technical knowledge reflecting the modern information society system;

- knowledge that forms the basis of research, cognitive activity;

- methods and actions that determine the operational basis of research, cognitive activity;

- research experience, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Леонтьев, Д.А. Ценность как междисциплинарное понятие: опыт многомерной реконструкции. [Текст] / Д.А. Леонтьев // Вопросы философии. – 1996. – №4. – С.15-26.
2. Макаренко, А.С. Воспитание гражданина [Текст] / Сост. Р.М. Бескина, М.Д. Виноградова. – М. : Просвещение, 1988. – 304 с.
3. Первин, Ю.А. Информационная культура информатика: слитно или отдельно? [Текст] / Ю.А. Первин // Информатика и образование. – 1995. – №3.
4. Ершов, А.П., Звенигородский Г.А., Первин Ю.А. Школьная информатика (концепции, состояние, перспективы) [Текст] / А.П. Ершов, Г.А. Звенигородский, Ю.А. Первин // Информатика и образование – 1995. – №1.
5. Зимняя, И. А. Ключевые компетенции – новая парадигма результата образования / И.А. Зимняя // Высшее образование сегодня. – 2003. – № 5.
6. Новиков, А. Возможности сетевой технологии в гражданском воспитании школьников [Текст] / А. Новиков, А. Прутченков // Воспитание школьников. – 2008. – №7. – С. 13-16. <https://www.openscience.uz/index.php/sciedu/article/view/845/832>.
7. Якиманская; И.С. Личностно-ориентированная технология в работе с учителем и учеником [Текст] // Экспериментальные площадки в московском образовании (МИПКРО). – М., 2001.
8. Хуторской, А.В. Ключевые компетенции как компонент личностно-ориентированной парадигмы образования // Ученик в обновляющейся школе [Текст] / Сборник научных трудов / Под ред. Ю.И. Дика, А.В. Хуторского. – М.: ИОСО РАО, 2002. – С.135-157.
9. Зеер, Э.Ф. Компетентный подход к образованию. [Электронный ресурс]. – <http://www.uroao.ru/konf2005.php?mode=&exmod=zeer>. (2005).
10. Холодная, М.А. Психология интеллекта [Текст] / М.А. Холодная. –Томск-Москва, 1997
11. Химматалиев Д.О. Касбий фаолиятга тайёргарликни диганостика қилишда педагогик ва техник билимлар интеграцияси. Монография. – Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон”. – 2018. – 168 б.